

Mini review

Histone deacetylase 4 (HDAC4), an epigenetic target for spinal muscular atrophy

Nevena TOMAŠEVIĆ

*University of Kragujevac, Faculty of Science, Kragujevac Center for Computational Biochemistry,
Department of Chemistry, Radoja Domanovića 12, 34000 Kragujevac, P.O. Box 60, Serbia*

Accepted: 29 August 2023 / Published online: 21 September 2023

Summary. Spinal muscular atrophy, a neurodegenerative recessive disease, is one of the leading genetic causes of death in early infancy and childhood worldwide, having an etiology in a mutation or deletion of the survival motor neuron 1 gene and deficient expression of the survival motor neuron protein. Being developed, spinal muscular atrophy is manifested in the denervation and consequent overexpression of histone deacetylase 4 in skeletal muscle, an epigenetic protein further having a role in the upregulation of two E3 ligases, atrogin-1 and MuRF1 via the myogenin-dependent pathway and leading to the structural and functional muscle protein breakdown through the ubiquitin-proteasome pathway. Being not medically treated, spinal muscular atrophy can progress toward the loss of movement and even death. Therefore, great efforts have been made so far to find an adequate therapy, with therapies already approved in Europe and the United States, yet of limited availability due to the high prices and severe side effects. In that sense, there are continuous efforts among the scientific community worldwide to develop novel, cost-efficient approaches in therapy. The development of selective histone deacetylase 4 inhibitors and their epigenetic modifying capabilities has been of high interest in an attempt to find potential candidates for the effective treatment of spinal muscular atrophy. Nevertheless, none of the histone deacetylase 4 inhibitors has been repurposed for treating spinal muscular atrophy.

Keywords: epigenetics, histone deacetylase 4, spinal muscular atrophy.

SPINAL MUSCULAR ATROPHY

Spinal muscular atrophy (SMA) is a rare, progressive neuromuscular disorder, and one of the leading genetic causes of death in early infancy and childhood (Lunke and El-Osta 2009; Kolb and Kissel 2015). Patients with SMA are born with the deficient expression of ubiquitously expressed survival motor neuron (SMN) protein, which plays a key role in the development of motor neurons, responsible for the transmission of signals from the brain and spinal cord, and enables the contraction of skeletal muscles, i.e., body movement.

Two nearly identical SMN genes expressed in human chromosome 5 at location 5q13 encode the SMN protein, a

telomeric SMN1 and a centromeric SMN2 (Kolb and Kissel 2015). The most functional SMN protein is transcribed and translated from the SMN1 gene, while the biosynthesis from the SMN2 gene produces only a small amount of fully functional protein due to C to T substitution in an exonic splicing enhancer, whereby exon 7 is excluded from the transcription, resulting in a formation of truncated and unfunctional SMN, rapidly degraded in the cell (Monani et al. 1999). Approximately 10–15% of mRNA SMN2 gene transcripts contain exon 7 and can produce full-length SMN protein. Individuals affected by SMA are deficient in a functional SMN1 gene, due to the mutation or deletion occurring at exon 7 (Lunke and El-Osta 2009; Evans et al. 2011). However, almost all individu-

als have at least one functional copy of the SMN2 gene and mostly have 2–4 of them, which can produce 10–20% of the usual level of the SMN protein, sufficient for the survival of some neurons. During the patient's life, the availability of the SMN protein reduces gradually in the anterior horn of the spinal cord and the brain, leading to the death of motor neuron cells. Consequently, skeletal muscles stop receiving the neural input from the central nervous system, normally obtained from these motor neurons, and exert less contractile activity, resulting in a decreased innervation (denervation).

A broad spectrum of SMA-diagnosed individuals is classified into clinical types based on the age of onset and disease progression (Kolb and Kissel 2015): Type 0 (usually fatal at birth); Type 1 (unable to sit independently; symptoms within the first few months of life); Type 2 (able to sit independently but not walk; symptoms between 7–18 months); Type 3 (independent walking; symptoms after 18 months) and Type 4 (independent walking and adult-onset). Moreover, the disease manifests in gradual but progressive muscle atrophy and loss of basic life functions, such as walking, digesting food, swallowing, and breathing. SMA does not affect the brain and cognitive functions (Day et al. 2022). Still, it is interesting to observe that SMA affects rather above-average intelligence and are very sociable newborns.

Not being medically treated, SMA leads to the progressive loss of movement and eventual death (Day et al. 2022). Three SMA drugs/therapies are currently approved by EMA (European Medicines Agency) and FDA (U.S. Food and Drug Administration): Spinraza™ (Nusinersen), developed by Biogen, Zolgensma™, developed by Novartis, and Evrysdi™ (risdiplam), developed by Roch. Hence, Spinraza™ represents an antisense oligonucleotide that modulates SMN2 splicing, via binding to a specific sequence in the SMN2 pre-mRNA and helps to increase the cellular concentration of stable SMN protein, therefore being an SMN-enhancing therapy (Kotulska et al. 2021). It is received by an intrathecal injection, directly into the cerebrospinal fluid through the lower back, four times within the first 2 months and every 4 months for the duration of the individual's life (maintenance doses). Despite being efficient, the medicine may cause serious unwanted effects (Erdos and Wild 2022).

Currently, the most efficient treatment for SMA, recommended for the administration to babies and young children under 2 years of age, is Zolgensma™ (onasemnogene abeparvovec-xioi). It is a medicament for so-called “gene therapy”, i.e., adeno-associated virus serotype 9 vector, designed to address the genetic root cause of SMA, by supplying the damaged neurons identical copies of SMN1 genes by *in vivo* transfection. This way, Zolgensma™ stimulates the SMN1 gene transcription, and consequent translation of new SMN proteins, thus replacing the missing or non-working SMN1

genes and restoring their function (Kotulska et al. 2021). It's a one-time intravenous infusion therapy, yet readily expensive (one treatment costs approximately 2.125 million US dollars). To date, the epidemiological profile on the effects of treatment with Zolgensma™ is heavily understudied, which is confirmed in the paper of Thielen et al. (2022). Nevertheless, distinct treatments may cause numerous side effects (Erdos and Wild 2022).

The treatment with Evrysdi™ (risdiplam) is for children two months and older, a daily oral SMN-enhancing therapy designed to increase SMN protein levels in the central nervous system and throughout the body. The active pharmaceutical ingredient is a small molecule, pyridazine derivative risdiplam, which modifies the splicing of SMN2 mRNA to include exon 7 and helps to increase the amount of stable SMN protein made by this gene *in vivo* (Poirier et al. 2018). However, the drug exerts several side effects, such as pneumonia, upper respiratory tract infections, etc. (Erdos and Wild 2022).

Due to the serious side- and off-target effects of listed drugs (as well as the high prices and the unavailability of Zolgensma™), there are continuous efforts among the scientific community worldwide to develop novel, cost-efficient approaches for the treatment of SMA. Hence, a palliative-type therapy for SMA could be developed using targeted inhibition or degradation of histone deacetylase 4 (HDAC4), owed to the HDAC4's affinity to upregulate the high expression of two E3 ligases, Muscle Atrophy F-box protein (MAFbx, also known as Atrogin-1 and FBXO32) and Muscle Ring finger protein-1 (MuRF1, also known as TRIM63), crucial for structural and functional muscle protein breakdown during the SMA progression. To understand the HDAC4's significance in the SMA ongoing, a profound understanding of epigenetics and the enzyme's topology, as well as the topography is required.

EPIGENETIC REGULATION OF EUKARYOTIC GENE TRANSCRIPTION

Epigenetics refers to reversible heritable changes in gene expression without alterations in the underlying DNA sequence, i.e., modifications of chromatin able to switch genes “on” or “off” and control the production of proteins (Suppl et al. 2019). Epigenetic machinery comprises various processes included in the regulation of DNA-nucleosome assembly for subsequent gene expression. Gene expression is regulated by proteins, involved in modifications on histones classified as writers, erasers, and readers (Suppl et al. 2019). Writers (e.g., DNA methyltransferases, histone methyltransferases, and histone acetyltransferases) regulate the covalent modifications of amino acid residues within the histone tails. Eras-

ers (histone deacetylases, histone demethylases, etc.), on the other hand, conduct the opposite process, the removal of covalent modifications from the histone tails. Finally, readers (i.e., bromodomain, chromodomain, and Tudor proteins) are enzymatically inactive, yet able to recognize and bind to specific epigenetic modifications, preventing writers and erasers from accessing specific modifications (Drake and Søreide 2019).

The acetylation of histone tails, mediated by histone acetyltransferases as writers, neutralizes the positive charge of the surface lysine residues within several histones (H2AK5, H2AK9, H2BK5, H2BK12, H2BK20, H3K4, H3K9, H3K14, H3K18, H3K23, H3K27, H3K36, H4K5, H4K8, H4K12, H4K16, H4K20), making the chromatin structure less compact (Zhao et al. 2022), weakening the interactions between histones and DNA, and enabling the RNA polymerase to access DNA and perform gene expression (Park and Kim 2020). On the other hand, histone deacetylases (HDACs) as erasers, remove the acetyl moiety from the ϵ -amino group of lysine residues on the N-terminal extension of the histone protein, enforcing the tight condensation between the chromatin and DNA, and minimizing the chances for RNA polymerase-catalyzed gene expression (Mohseni et al. 2013). Published data show that silencing of HDAC by inhibitors VPA (targeting HDAC1, HDAC2, and HDAC3), PBA (targeting HDAC1 and HDAC2), M344 (targeting HDAC6), LBH589 (panHDAC inhibitor), SAHA (targeting HDAC1, HDAC2, HDAC3, HDAC8, and HDAC9), TSA (targeting HDAC5), romidepsin (targeting HDAC1 and HDAC2), resveratrol (targeting HDAC8), and curcumin (targeting HDAC8), act beneficially on the transcription machinery to the SMN2 promoter, by increasing the transcription activity at the SMN2 promoter and exon 7 inclusion (Evans et al. 2011; Mohseni et al. 2013). Consequently, treatment with the aforementioned inhibitors increases the transcription of mRNA bearing the genetic information for exon 7, resulting in an increased SMN expression. Unfortunately, most of these inhibitors exert severe side effects after treatment and this is a disadvantage for their use.

In addition to their essential role in gene transcription, histone acetyltransferases, and HDACs influence other cellular pathways as well, like differentiation, apoptosis, cell cycle control, signaling, and DNA repair through the modification of non-histone proteins (Lunke and El-Osta 2009).

An imbalance between histone acetyltransferases and HDAC activities can affect the improper expression of a specific gene, and result in genomic instability and epigenetic diseases (Park and Kim 2020). Therefore, the precise control of histone acetyltransferases and HDACs is required for the regulated expression of various genes associated with signal transduction, cell growth, and cell death.

HISTONE DEACETYLASES

Histone deacetylases, a subject of this paper, are a large family of proteases ubiquitously distributed within bacteria, fungi, plants, and animals (Silvestri et al. 2012). To date, at least 18 HDAC isoforms have been discovered in mammals, divided into four distinct classes (I, II, III, and IV) according to size, sequence homology, number of active sites, and localization in the cell. Classes I, II, and IV are zinc-dependent amidohydrolases, whereas class III members require NAD⁺ as a cofactor for their catalytic activity (Park and Kim 2020). The members of class I, HDAC1, 2, 3, and 8, are predominantly expressed in the nucleus. The class II HDACs, namely HDAC4, 5, 6, 7, 9, and 10, are nucleocytoplasmic shuttling proteins, further divided, according to the domain organization, into class IIa (HDAC4, HDAC5, HDAC7, and HDAC9) and class IIb (HDAC6 and HDAC10). As for class I, Class IIa HDACs are extended with ~600 residues on the N-terminus, while the class IIb enzymes contain two catalytic domains (Bottomley et al. 2008). Class III is comprised of sirtuins (silent information regulators, SIRs) SIRT1-7, while class IV includes only HDAC11, as it is not highly homologous with yeast deacetylases. Besides histones, HDACs have shown the ability to deacetylate nonhistone proteins, predominantly transcription factors (Bottomley et al. 2008).

HDAC4: EXPRESSION, LOCALIZATION, SUBSTRATE SPECIFICITY, AND STRUCTURAL FEATURES

The highest expression of HDAC4 occurs in the brain, heart, and skeletal muscle. Different from other HDACs, it is localized both in the nucleus and cytoplasm and is an epigenetic regulator of diverse cellular functions (Wang et al. 2014). Its location in cells depends on an HDAC4 phosphorylation status, mediated by diverse kinases, namely, calcium/calmodulin-dependent protein kinase (CaMK), extracellular signal-regulated kinases 1 and 2, AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK), and glycogen synthase kinase 3, as well as by proteolytic cleavage mediated by caspases (Huang et al. 2022). The non-phosphorylated form is the most abundant in the nucleus, whereas the phosphorylated form of the enzyme is located in the cytoplasm. Following phosphorylation, after binding to the chaperone protein 14-3-3, or HDAC4 shuttles from the nucleus to the cytoplasm (Fig. 1).

As a nuclear target, HDAC4 performs regulation of gene expression, cell growth, and proliferation. Still, its overexpression can lead to cancer development, like colon cancer, esophageal squamous cell carcinoma, gastric cancer, B-cell lymphoma, urothelial carcinoma, hepatocellular carcinoma, gliomas, etc. (Halkidou et al. 2004; Wilson et al. 2008; Ahmad et al. 2015; Amodio et al. 2016; Zeng et al.

Fig 1. Upregulation of spinal muscular atrophy by HDAC4.

2016; Marampon et al. 2017; Milazzo et al. 2020). On the other hand, within the cytoplasm, HDAC4 is an important target for the treatment of cardiovascular, neurodegenerative, and muscle diseases (Wang et al. 2014; Ma et al. 2021; Huang et al. 2022).

The subcellular location of HDAC4 enables the deacetylation of the acetyl group from both histones and nonhistone proteins and consequently dictates the physiology and pathological role of the enzyme within cells and tissues. Still, the enzyme lacks substrate specificity, as it, differently from other HDACs, exerts very low enzymatic activity against acetylated lysine-containing histones likely due to the unique catalytic domain structural features (see below) (Bottomley et al. 2008). However, HDAC4 exerts the ability to deacetylate non-histone proteins: myosin heavy chain, peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma co-activator 1 alpha (PGC-1 α), and heat shock cognate 71 kDa protein (Luo et al. 2019).

In general, HDAC4 shares conserved topology with other zinc-dependent HDAC isoforms, where the experimentally resolved crystal structures complexed with either hydroxamic acid inhibitors (PDB IDs: 2VQM (Bottomley et al. 2008), 2VQV (Bottomley et al. 2008), 4CBT (Bürli et al. 2013) and 6FYZ (Luckhurst et al. 2019)), trifluoromethylketone inhibitors 2VQJ (wild-type protein) (Bottomley et al. 2008), 2VQQ (mutated protein), and 2VQO (mutated protein) (Bottomley et al. 2008), and 4CBY (Bürli et al. 2013),

and tetrasubstituted cyclopropane inhibitors (5A2S) (Luckhurst et al. 2016) reveal a hydrophobic channel leading to the enzyme active site that nests Asp196, Asp290, His198, and two water molecules coordinated to the catalytic Zn²⁺ ion (PDB ID: 2VQM, Fig. 2).

At the entrance of the catalytic site, there is another zinc-binding domain, specific only for the HDAC4 and other class IIa HDACs, which makes the active site more accessible compared to the other isoforms (Bottomley et al. 2008; Park and Kim 2020). Within the active site of HDAC8 (PDB ID: 1W22) or HDAC6 (PDB ID: 5EDU), the acetamide carbonyl group of the acetylated lysine substrate replaces one water molecule and forms a hydrogen bond with the hydroxyl group of a tyrosine residue (Tyr306 in HDAC8, or Tyr782 in HDAC6), important for the stabilization of acetylated substrate via a tetrahedral intermediate (Fig. 2). However, in the binding pocket of HDAC4 (PDB ID: 2VQM) tyrosine (Tyr306/782), is replaced with histidine (His332) and rotated away from the binding site amino acids, leading to the change in the active site size, and the weaker stabilization of the acetylated substrate (PDB ID: 2VQM) in comparison to the other zinc-dependent deacetylases (HDAC8, PDB ID: 1W22 or HDAC6, PDB ID: 5EDU). Thus, reduced HDAC4 catalytic activity could be attributed to a Tyr306/782 to His332 active site mutation (Park and Kim 2020).

The unique characteristic of all class IIa HDAC members is an adapter domain in the N-terminus involved in

Fig. 2. Crystal structures comparison between the HDAC4 (beige chain, PDB ID: 2VQM, active site amino acids Asp196, His198, Asp290, His332, and His 158 and 159 involved in stabilization of water molecule), HDAC6 (violet chain, PDB ID: 5EDU, active site amino acids Asp649, His659, Asp742, Tyr782), and HDAC8 (blue chain, PDB ID: 1W22, active site amino acids Asp178, His180, Asp267, Tyr306).

binding to DNA via MEF2 transcription factor, which in addition enables enzyme phosphorylation, association with 14-3-3 proteins, and further shuttling between the cytoplasm and nucleus (Park and Kim 2020).

HDAC4 INVOLVEMENT IN SMA AND OTHER MUSCULAR DISORDERS (DENERVATING DISEASES)

As indicated above, SMA is characterized by motor neuron loss, skeletal weakness, and severe atrophy (Bricceno et al. 2012). During muscle atrophy, an increased expression of specific E3 ubiquitin ligases, atrogin-1 and MuRF1, occurs (Fig. 1), together with HDAC4 and myogenin as the upstream regulators (Bricceno et al. 2012). Thus, the atrogin-1 is involved in muscle growth and differentiation for

degradation, whereas MuRF1 mediates the degradation of structural proteins, such as myosin heavy chain proteins, myosin light chains 1 and 2, myosin binding protein C, muscle creatine kinase, and other myofibrillar proteins. The high expression of distinct E3 ligases leads to structural and functional muscle protein degradation (breakdown) through the ubiquitin-proteasome pathway.

In more detail, an increment of HDAC4 following denervation suppresses the expression of transcription factor (TF) Dach2, a negative regulator of the myogenin promoter, and ends with increased myogenin expression (Fig. 1). Myogenin is a muscle-specific TF (regulatory protein) involved in myogenesis and is essential for muscle development, thus playing a dual role as both an inducer of neurogenic atrophy and a regulator of muscle development. HDAC4 can be positively regulated by myogenin, as well, via microRNA

involved in skeletal muscle development (miRNA-206) and can improve the ability of motor neurons in SMA patients and maintain the shape and number of the motor endplate in skeletal muscle (Ma et al. 2021).

In addition to the upregulation of atrogenes expression, HDAC4 is involved in the regulation of PGC-1 α , a transcriptional cofactor important for energy metabolism and mitochondrial biogenesis (Luo et al. 2019). The regulation is based on the deacetylation of PGC-1 α by HDAC4 and the decrease of PGC-1 α level in myotubes.

This approach aiming to stop muscle denervation and degradation, the most severe symptoms of SMA by inhibiting HDAC4 has not been widely investigated, and it is completely different from the mechanism of action of previously published HDAC inhibitors, responsible for enhancing the SMN protein expression (Mohseni et al. 2013). Due to insufficient examination of HDAC4 as a target for SMA, the outcome can't be predicted.

AN OVERVIEW OF HDAC4 INHIBITORS

Denervation and other spinal muscular atrophy adverse effects can be mitigated by suppression of myogenin-dependent atrogenes induction with HDAC4 selective inhibitors. Currently, besides the co-crystallized ones (Table 1), there are several classes of HDAC4 inhibitors, that still exert a low degree of isoform selectivity, and, to date, none of them have

been tested against SMA (Table 2). For that reason, the development of selective HDAC4 inhibitors is one of the most pressing concerns to be addressed to minimize off-target toxicity (Park and Kim 2020). With selective HDAC4 inhibitors, the HDAC4-Dach2-myogenin pathway could be pharmacologically targeted to suppress atrogenes induction and muscle protein breakdown.

CONCLUSION

HDAC4 appears to be an important enzyme in the regulation of spinal muscular atrophy and its inhibition could ameliorate the denervation and muscle decomposition within the proteasome pathway. Of currently available more than seventy HDAC4 inhibitors of which many of them (if not most of them) lack selectivity, none have been tested against SMA. Thus, the potential SMA treatment with HDAC4 inhibitors remains an unexplored field of medicinal chemistry, with great potential for further drug development.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was supported by the Serbian Ministry of Science, Technological Development, and Innovation (Agreement Nos. 451-03-47/2023-01/200122 and 451-03-47/2023-01/200378)

Table 1. An overview of compounds co-crystallized with HDAC4.

Structure	Activity (Ref.)	Structure	Activity (Ref.)
	IC ₅₀ : 50 - 60 nM (Bürli et al. 2013)		
	IC ₅₀ : 20 nM (Bürli et al. 2013)		
	IC ₅₀ : 39 nM K _d : 39 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)		

Table 2. Structures and activities of the literature available HDAC4 inhibitors.

Structure	Activity (Ref.)	Structure	Activity (Ref.)
	IC_{50} : 54 nM (Asfaha et al. 2019)		
Tasquinimod			
	IC_{50} : 10 nM (Asfaha et al. 2019)		
Quisinostat			
	IC_{50} : 41 μ M (Macabuag et al. 2022)		
LMK-235			
	IC_{50} : 0.50 μ M (Tessier et al. 2009)		
CUDC-101		LAQ	
	IC_{50} : 0.18 μ M (Luckhurst et al. 2016)		
Pracinostat (SB939)			
	IC_{50} : 50 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2016)		
TMP195			
	IC_{50} : 0.11 μ M (Luckhurst et al. 2016)		
TMP269			

Structure	Activity (Ref.)	Structure	Activity (Ref.)
	IC_{50} : 20 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2016)		
	IC_{50} : 150 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2016)		
	IC_{50} : 30 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2016)		
	IC_{50} : 140 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2016)		
	IC_{50} : 40 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2016)		
	IC_{50} : 80 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2016)		
	IC_{50} : 40 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2016)		

Structure	Activity (Ref.)	Structure	Activity (Ref.)
	IC ₅₀ : 30 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2016)		
	IC ₅₀ : 10 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2016)		
	IC ₅₀ : 0.33 μM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)		
	IC ₅₀ : 22 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)		
	IC ₅₀ : 103 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)		
	IC ₅₀ : 33 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)		
	IC ₅₀ : 31 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)		
	IC ₅₀ : 22 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)		

Structure	Activity (Ref.)	Structure	Activity (Ref.)
	<p>IC₅₀: 40 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)</p>		
	<p>IC₅₀: 30 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)</p>		
	<p>IC₅₀: 22 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)</p>		
	<p>IC₅₀: 25 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)</p>		
	<p>IC₅₀: 57 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)</p>		
	<p>IC₅₀: 55 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)</p>		
	<p>IC₅₀: 49 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)</p>		
	<p>IC₅₀: 25 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)</p>		

Structure	Activity (Ref.)	Structure	Activity (Ref.)
	IC ₅₀ : 25 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)		
	IC ₅₀ : 17 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)		
TMP942			IC ₅₀ : 54 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)
	K _i : 23.8 μM (Asfaha et al. 2019)		
TMP974			IC ₅₀ : 119 nM (Luckhurst et al. 2019)
	IC ₅₀ : 18 nM (Asfaha et al. 2019)		
	IC ₅₀ : 14.9 μM (Hsu et al. 2017)		
	IC ₅₀ : 10 nM (Macabuag et al. 2022)	A226640 Sulfone	
	IC ₅₀ : 2.5 μM (Hsu et al. 2017)		
KD 5170		A364365	
	IC ₅₀ : 49 nM (Luo et al. 2019)		
		NVS-HD2	

Structure	Activity (Ref.)	Structure	Activity (Ref.)
<p>A159452 Catechol</p>	IC ₅₀ : 320 nM (Giorgio et al. 2015)		
<p>A159452 Catechol</p>	IC ₅₀ : 4.4 μM (Hsu et al. 2017)		

REFERENCES

- Ahmad A, Ginnebaugh KR, Yin S, Bollig-Fischer A, Reddy KB, Sarkar FH. 2015. Functional role of miR-10b in tamoxifen resistance of ER-positive breast cancer cells through down-regulation of HDAC4. *BMC Cancer*. 15(1):1–10.
- Amodio N, Stamato MA, Gullà AM, Morelli E, Romeo E, Raimondi L, Pitari MR, Ferrandino I, Misso G, Caraglia M, et al. 2016. Therapeutic targeting of miR-29b/HDAC4 epigenetic loop in multiple myeloma. *Molecular Cancer Therapeutics*. 15(6):1364–1375.
- Arts J, King P, Mariën A, Floren W, Belien A, Janssen L, Pilatte I, Roux B, Decrane L, Gilissen R, et al. 2009. JNJ-26481585, a novel “second-generation” oral histone deacetylase inhibitor, shows broad-spectrum preclinical antitumoral activity. *Clinical Cancer Research*. 15(22):6841–6851.
- Asfaha Y, Schrenk C, Avelar LAA, Hamacher A, Pflieger M, Kassack MU, Kurz T. 2019. Recent advances in class IIa histone deacetylases research. *Bioorganic and Medicinal Chemistry*. 27(22):115087.
- Bottomley MJ, Lo Surdo P, Di Giovine P, Cirillo A, Scarpelli R, Ferrigno F, Jones P, Neddermann P, De Francesco R, Steinkühler C, et al. 2008. Structural and functional analysis of the human HDAC4 catalytic domain reveals a regulatory structural zinc-binding domain. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 283(39):26694–26704.
- Bricceno KV, Sampognaro PJ, Van Meerbeke JP, Sumner CJ, Fischbeck KH, Burnett BG. 2012. Histone deacetylase inhibition suppresses myogenin-dependent atrogenic activation in spinal muscular atrophy mice. *Human Molecular Genetics*. 21(20):4448–4459.
- Bürli RW, Luckhurst CA, Aziz O, Matthews KL, Yates D, Lyons KA, Beconi M, McAllister G, Breccia P, Stott AJ, et al. 2013. Design, synthesis, and biological evaluation of potent and selective class IIa histone deacetylase (HDAC) inhibitors as a potential therapy for Huntington's disease. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*. 56(24):9934–9954.
- Day JW, Howell K, Place A, Long K, Rossello J, Kertesz N, Nomikos G. 2022. Advances and limitations for the treatment of spinal muscular atrophy. *BMC Pediatrics*. 22(1):632.
- Di Giorgio E, Gagliostro E, Brancolini C. 2015. Selective class IIa HDAC inhibitors: myth or reality. *Cellular and Molecular Life Sciences*. 72:73–86.
- Drake TM, Soreide K. 2019. Cancer epigenetics in solid organ tumours: A primer for surgical oncologists. *European Journal of Surgical Oncology*. 45(5):736–746.
- Erdos J, Wild C. 2022. Mid- and long-term (at least 12 months) follow-up of patients with spinal muscular atrophy (SMA) treated with nusinersen, onasemnogene abeparvovec, risdiplam or combination therapies: A systematic review of real-world study data. *European Journal of Paediatric Neurology*. 39:1–10.
- Evans MC, Cherry JJ, Androphy EJ. 2011. Differential regulation of the SMN2 gene by individual HDAC proteins. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*. 414(1):25–30.
- Halkidou K, Cook S, Leung HY, Neal DE, Robson CN. 2004. Nuclear accumulation of histone deacetylase 4 (HDAC4) coincides with the loss of androgen sensitivity in hormone refractory cancer of the prostate. *European Urology*. 45(3):382–389.
- Hsu KC, Liu CY, Lin TE, Hsieh JH, Sung TY, Tseng HJ, Yang JM, Huang WJ. 2017. Novel class IIa-selective histone deacetylase inhibitors discovered using an in silico virtual screening approach. *Scientific Reports*. 7(1):3228.
- Huang C, Lin Z, Liu X, Ding Q, Cai J, Zhang Z, Rose P, Zhu YZ. 2022. HDAC4 inhibitors as antivascular senescence therapeutics. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*. 2022:3087916.
- Kassis H, Shehadah A, Li C, Zhang Y, Cui Y, Roberts C, Sadry N, Liu X, Chopp M, Zhang ZG. 2016. Class IIa histone deacetylases affect neuronal remodeling and functional outcome after stroke. *Neurochemistry International*. 96:24–31.
- Katarzyna K, Aviva F-V, Jana H. 2021. Recombinant Adeno-associated virus serotype 9 gene therapy in spinal muscular atrophy. *Frontiers in Neurology*. 12:726468.
- Kolb SJ, Kissel JT. 2015. Spinal muscular atrophy. *Neurologic Clinics*. 33(4):831–846.
- Kotulska K, Fattal-Valevski A, Haberlova J. 2021. Recombinant adeno-associated virus serotype 9 gene therapy in spinal muscular atrophy. *Frontiers in Neurology*. 12:726468.
- Liang T, Wang F, Elhassan RM, Cheng Y, Tang X, Chen W, Fang H, Hou X. 2023. Targeting histone deacetylases for cancer therapy: Trends and challenges. *Acta Pharmaceutica Sinica B*. 13(6):2425–2463.
- Luckhurst CA, Aziz O, Beaumont V, Bürli RW, Breccia P, Maillard MC, Haughan AF, Lamers M, Leonard P, Matthews KL, et al. 2019. Development and characterization of a CNS-penetrant benzhydryl hydroxamic acid class IIa histone deacetylase inhibitor. *Bioorganic and Medicinal Chemistry Letters*. 29(1):83–88.
- Luckhurst CA, Breccia P, Stott AJ, Aziz O, Birch HL, Bürli RW, Hughes SJ, Jarvis RE, Lamers M, Leonard PM, et al. 2016. Potent, selective, and CNS-penetrant tetrasubstituted cyclopropane class IIa histone deacetylase (HDAC) inhibitors. *ACS Medicinal Chemistry Letters*. 7(1):34–39.
- Lunke S, El-Osta A. 2009. The emerging role of epigenetic modifications

- and chromatin remodeling in spinal muscular atrophy. *Journal of Neurochemistry*. 109(6):1557–1569.
- Luo L, Martin SC, Parkington J, Cadena SM., Zhu J, Ibejunjo C, Summermatter S, Londraville N, Patora-Komisarska K, Widler L, et al. 2019. HDAC4 controls muscle homeostasis through deacetylation of myosin heavy chain, PGC-1 α , and Hsc70. *Cell Reports*. 29(3):749–763.
- Ma W, Cai Y, Shen Y, Chen X, Zhang L, Ji Y, Chen Z, Zhu J, Yang X, Sun H. 2021. HDAC4 knockdown alleviates denervation-induced muscle atrophy by inhibiting myogenin-dependent atrogenes activation. *Frontiers in Cellular Neuroscience*. 15:663384.
- Macabuag N, Esmieu W, Breccia P, Jarvis R, Blackaby W, Lazari O, Urbonas L, Eznarriaga M, Williams R, Strijbosch A, et al. 2022. Developing HDAC4-selective protein degraders to investigate the role of HDAC4 in Huntington's disease pathology. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*. 65(18):12445–12459.
- Mak JYW, Wu K-C, Gupta PK, Barbero S, McLaughlin MG, Lucke AJ, Tng J, Lim J, Loh Z, Sweet MJ, et al. 2021. HDAC7 inhibition by phenacetyl and phenylbenzoyl hydroxamates. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*. 64(4):2186–2204.
- Marampon F, Megiorni F, Camero S, Crescioli C, McDowell HP, Sferra R, Vetuschi A, Pompili S, Ventura L, De Felice F, et al. 2017. HDAC4 and HDAC6 sustain DNA double strand break repair and stem-like phenotype by promoting radioresistance in glioblastoma cells. *Cancer Letters*. 397:1–11.
- Milazzo G, Mercatelli D, Di Muzio G, Triboli L, De Rosa P, Perini G, Giorgi FM. 2020. Histone deacetylases (HDACs): Evolution, specificity, role in transcriptional complexes, and pharmacological actionability. *Genes*. 11(5):556.
- Mohseni J, Zabidi-Hussin ZA, Sasongko TH. 2013. Histone deacetylase inhibitors as potential treatment for spinal muscular atrophy. *Genetics and Molecular Biology*. 36(3):299–307.
- Monani UR, Lorson CL, Parsons DW, Prior TW, Androphy EJ, Burghes AH, McPherson JD. 1999. A single nucleotide difference that alters splicing patterns distinguishes the SMA gene SMN1 from the copy gene SMN2. *Human Molecular Genetics*. 8(7):1177–1183.
- Park SY, Kim JS. 2020. A short guide to histone deacetylases including recent progress on class II enzymes. *Experimental and Molecular Medicine*. 52:204–212.
- Payne JE, Bonnefous C, Hassig CA, Symons KT, Guo X, Nguyen P-M, Annable T, Wash PL, Hoffman TZ, Rao TS, et al. 2008. Identification of KD5170: A novel mercaptoketone-based histone deacetylase inhibitor. *Bioorganic and Medicinal Chemistry Letters*. 18(23):6093–6096.
- Poirier A, Weetall M, Heinig K, Bucheli F, Schoenlein K, Alsenz J, Bassett S, Ullah M, Senn C, Ratni H, et al. 2018. Risdiplam distributes and increases SMN protein in both the central nervous system and peripheral organs. *Pharmacology Research and Perspectives*. 6(6):e00447.
- Robinson DCL, Dilworth FJ. 2018. Epigenetic regulation of adult myogenesis. *Current Topics in Developmental Biology*. 126:235–284.
- Silvestri L, Ballante F, Mai A, Marshall GR, Ragno R. 2012. Histone deacetylase inhibitors: structure-based modeling and isoform-selectivity prediction. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*. 52(8):2215–2235.
- Sippl W, Jung M, editors. 2019. *Epigenetic drug discovery (Methods & Principles in Medicinal Chemistry)*, 1st ed. Wiley-VCH.
- Tessier P, Smil DV, Wahhab A, Leit S, Rahil J, Li Z, Déziel R, Besterman JM. 2009. Diphenylmethylene hydroxamic acids as selective class IIa histone deacetylase inhibitors. *Bioorganic and Medicinal Chemistry Letters*. 19(19):5684–5688.
- Thielen FW, Heine RJS, van den Berg S, ten Ham RMT, Uyl-de Groot CA. 2022. Towards sustainability and affordability of expensive cell and gene therapies? Applying a cost-based pricing model to estimate prices for Libmeldy and Zolgensma. *Cytotherapy*. 24(12):1245–1258.
- Tilekar K, Hess JD, Upadhyay N, Schweipert M, Flath F, Gutierrez DA, Loiodice F, Lavecchia A, Meyer-Almes F-J, Aguilera RJ, et al. 2021. Inhibitors with cyclic linker and non-hydroxamate zinc binding group: Design, synthesis, HDAC screening and in vitro cytotoxicity evaluation. *ChemistrySelect*. 6:6748.
- Wang Z, Qin G, Zhao TC. 2014. HDAC4: mechanism of regulation and biological functions. *Epigenomics*. 6(1):139–150.
- Wilson AJ, Byun DS, Nasser S, Murray LB, Ayyanar K, Arango D, Figueroa M, Melnick A, Kao GD, Augenlicht LH, et al. 2008. HDAC4 promotes growth of colon cancer cells via repression of p21. *Molecular Biology of the Cell*. 19(10):4062–4075.
- Zeng LS, Yang XZ, Wen YF, Mai SJ, Wang MH, Zhang MY, Zheng XF, Wang HY. 2016. Overexpressed HDAC4 is associated with poor survival and promotes tumor progression in esophageal carcinoma. *Aging (Albany NY)*. 8(6):1236.
- Zhao L, Islam R, Wang Y, Zhang X, Liu L-Z. 2022. Epigenetic regulation in chromium-, nickel- and cadmium-induced carcinogenesis. *Cancers*. 14:5768.